

AN ANALYSIS ON VIEWS OF PROSPECTIVE TURKISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS ON PEER ASSESSMENTⁱ

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Abstract:

This study has been conducted to examine the views of prospective Turkish language teachers on peer assessment. For this research, 47 prospective Turkish language teachers who are junior student (3rd grade) in Department of Turkish Language of Atatürk University have participated in this study. Views of prospective teachers on peer assessment have been compiled by means of structured interview form. The obtained data has been interpreted by applying content analysis method with considering the questions of interview form. In the study, it has been understood that many of the prospective teachers have positive views on peer assessment. Prospective teachers have stated that they realize their inadequate aspects, they can empathize, a democratic environment has developed, there has been increase in their self-confidence, they can get feedback and socialize through peer assessment. Despite these positive aspects, the prospective teachers have emphasized that acting upon emotions and lack of self-confidence are the negative aspects of peer assessment.

Keywords: prospective Turkish language teachers, peer assessment, Turkish language education

1. Introduction

From the earliest periods of societies, their lives, beliefs, and feelings can be transmitted to the future through the mother tongue. Without any document, information about idea, belief, economic activities, fashion/clothes, eating/dietary habits, war equipment, neighborhood relations etc. can be obtained by means of vocabulary of the mother tongue. Therefore, it can be said that mother tongue is the genetic memory of societies.

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The mother tongue teachers have significant tasks for the genetic memory not to be interrupted. Perhaps, the most significant part of these tasks is to make the language interesting for students. Traditional assessment is one of the significant concerns that constitute a prejudice in the students in the mother tongue course as well as in the other courses. In the traditional measurement and assessment applications, while the students are assessed, output-oriented assessment is made, and written and oral surveys with elective/short answer tests are applied (Gelbal and Kelecioğlu, 2007, p. 136). In order to save students from this anxiety, the link between assessment and lifelong learning should be established and alternative assessment methods should be applied (Boud and Falchikov, 2005). One of these methods is peer assessment.

Peer is defined as “*Each individual who is equal in terms of age, occupation, social situation, etc.*” (Turkish Language Institution [TDK], 2011, p. 72) and assessment is defined as “*Assessment work, evaluation*” (TDK, 2011, page 608). From these definitions, peer assessment is the assessment of individuals who have similar status, same occupation, and age close to each other. According to Alıcı (2008), peer assessment is the assessment of students’ studies (research, homework, project, etc.) by other students in the teaching process. During the peer assessment, the students’ understanding and adoption of the criteria is very important for the achievement of the peer assessment process (Koç, 2011).

It has been stated that peer assessment in the literature has various positive effects on the students. These have been mentioned below.

- Increases student motivation thanks to the sense of ownership.
- Ensure that learners take responsibility as autonomous individuals.
- Allows students to see mistakes as new opportunities rather than failures.
- Provides practicality in the assessment skills of students.
- Provides a model for self-assessments of students.
- Encourages in-depth learning instead of superficial learning (Brown, Rust and Gibbs, 1994; Zariski, 1996; Race, 1998).

Despite its positive effects, it has been determined that some problems may be encountered if necessary conditions are not satisfied in peer assessment in various researches. These problems are:

- In case of carrying out assessment in incorrect way,
- Systematic prejudice,
- Lack of experience,
- Frivolity,
- Assessment standards cannot be defined correctly (Zayed, 2017, p. 590).

The aim of this study is to determine the views, attitudes and recommendations of prospective Turkish language teachers about peer assessment. Three main research questions have been asked in this direction. The questions have been mentioned below.

- What are the positive and negative views of prospective Turkish language teachers on peer assessment?
- How are prospective Turkish language teachers' attitudes towards peer assessment?

- What are the recommendations for peer assessment of prospective Turkish language teachers?

2. Method

In this part, information on research design, working group, data collection and analysis of data has been introduced.

2.1 Research Design

Qualitative research design has been applied in this study which was conducted in the screening model in order to reveal the views of peer assessment of prospective Turkish language teachers who are studying in Atatürk University. *“Qualitative research can be fined as a research process in which qualitative data collection methods such as observation, interview and document analysis are applied, and facts and incidents are presented in a natural, realistic and holistic manner”* (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2008, p. 39). The most fundamental features of qualitative research are natural environment, direct data collection, being process-oriented with enhanced description, holistic data analysis, reflection of participants' perspectives and resilient research design (Büyüköztürk, Kılıç-Çakmak, Akgün, Karadeniz and Demirel, 2008, p. 49).

2.2 Working group

The research has been carried out in the department of Turkish Language Education at Atatürk University in the spring semester of 2016-2017 academic years with participation of 47 prospective Turkish language teachers who were studying at the 3rd (junior) grade.

Convenience sampling as one of the purposeful samplings has been applied in the study since prospective Turkish language teachers studying in Atatürk University are available and volunteer for participating in the study. *“This type of sampling is related to availability of the participants and easiness to include individuals and groups into the research process”* (Ekiz, 2009, p. 106)

2.3 Data Collection and Analysis

A semi-structured interview form has been applied to collect the data. *“The Form for Determining the Views of the Prospective Turkish Language Teachers on the Peer Assessment”* prepared by the researchers and it has been filled by the prospective Turkish language teachers.

The data has been embedded in codes that were determined by the researchers in order to establish the views of prospective Turkish language teachers on peer assessment. Aftermath of the literature review, the codes have been prepared with considering the recommendations of two Turkish language educational specialists at final stage. Then, views of the students have been categorized under these codes. To ensure the reliability of the study, two separate scorer data have been examined.

Examples have been given among the views of prospective Turkish language teachers to support the data.

3. Findings

In this part, the findings obtained from the views of prospective Turkish language teachers have been shown.

Table 1: Views on Definition of Peer Assessment

Codes	Student/s	f
Peer Assessment	S ₁ , S ₃ , S ₅ , S ₆ , S ₇ , S ₈ , S ₁₀ , S ₁₁ , S ₁₃ , S ₁₄ , S ₁₅ , S ₁₆ , S ₁₈ , S ₁₉ , S ₂₀ , S ₂₁ , S ₂₃ , S ₂₄ , S ₂₅ , S ₂₆ , S ₂₈ , S ₂₉ , S ₃₀ , S ₃₁ , S ₃₂ , S ₃₃ , S ₃₅ , S ₃₆ , S ₃₇ , S ₃₈ , S ₃₉ , S ₄₁ , S ₄₂ , S ₄₄ , S ₄₆ , S ₄₇	36
Evaluation of In-Class Activities	S ₄ , S ₆ , S ₂₂ , S ₂₇ , S ₃₄ , S ₄₃	6
Peer Comparison	S ₂ , S ₁₇ , S ₄₀ , S ₄₅	4
Alternative Measurement Tool	S ₆ , S ₉ , S ₁₂	3
Realizing Negative and Positive Aspects	S ₁₆	1

Table 1 has shown views of prospective Turkish language teachers on definition of peer assessment. When Table 1 is examined, it is seen that prospective Turkish language teachers consider peer assessment under five titles. These are peer assessment, evaluation of in-class activities, peer comparison, alternative measurement tools, realizing positive and negative aspects. Among these, assessment of peers has been mostly seen under *f*: 36 title and realizing negative and positive aspects has been least mentioned under *f*: 1 title. Some views that expressed by the students can be introduced as follows:

S₁: "Peer assessments are evaluations that made by individuals who are at the same age. They assess the studies that carried out by each other."

S₆: "It covers the process of evaluating each other. Assessment means evaluation of a project, assignments, in-class activities etc. that carried out by the students."

S₁₂: "It means developing individual views of each prospective teacher with applying alternative measurement and assessment tools and methods."

S₁₆: "It means assessment of students in terms of particular criteria and establishing negative and positive aspects of each other."

S₁₇: "Peer assessment is a comparison that made by an individual to compare herself/himself with her/his peers at the same age and same intelligence level."

Table 2: Views on Points that Should Be Taken into Consideration While Making Peer Assessment

Codes	Student/s	f
Justice	S ₃ , S ₄ , S ₅ , S ₆ , S ₉ , S ₁₇ , S ₂₃ , S ₂₄ , S ₂₈ , S ₂₉ , S ₃₀ , S ₃₁ , S ₃₂ , S ₃₃ , S ₃₄ , S ₃₅ , S ₃₇ , S ₃₉ , S ₄₂	19
Scientificness / Objectivity	S ₂ , S ₅ , S ₈ , S ₁₄ , S ₁₆ , S ₁₈ , S ₂₀ , S ₂₁ , S ₂₇ , S ₃₈ , S ₄₁ , S ₄₃	12
Scoring Rubric (Rubric)	S ₃ , S ₈ , S ₁₀ , S ₁₃ , S ₁₄ , S ₁₅ , S ₂₂ , S ₃₂ , S ₄₇	9
Individual Differences	S ₉ , S ₁₂ , S ₁₇ , S ₁₉ , S ₃₅ , S ₄₂ , S ₄₆	7
Expediency	S ₁₆ , S ₂₆ , S ₃₀ , S ₃₆ , S ₄₄	5
Gender	S ₄₀ , S ₄₅ , S ₄₆	3
Scrutinizing Questions	S ₂ , S ₁₁ , S ₂₅	3
Moral Values	S ₁ , S ₇	2
Observation	S ₆	1
Teacher guidance	S ₆	1
Empathy	S ₂₃	1

Table 2 has shown the views of the prospective Turkish language teachers on points to be considered while scoring in the peer assessment. When Table 2 is examined, it is seen that the prospective Turkish language teachers have determined 10 titles under consideration when scoring in peer assessment. These are justice, objectivity, forming scoring rubric, individual difference, expediency, gender, scrutinizing questions, moral values, and observation and teacher guidance. Among these, the views on justice have been mostly expressed under *f*: 19 title, while views on observation and teacher guidance have been least expressed under *f*: 2 title. It is possible to present some of the views expressed by the students as follows:

S₃: "When grading, students should be asked to fairly score, and students should justify their reasons in what extent."

S₉: "First of all, it should be without prejudice and should not be held sides. The assessment should cover every aspect of the peer. For example; the level of knowledge and nonverbal movements are evaluated if speech evaluation is made. Individual differences, deficiencies or extra abilities must be considered."

S₁₈: "S/he should not consider feelings and thoughts and should act in objective manner."

S₂₆: "S/he should make assessment with considering success level, how teacher teach."

S₄₀: "I think it is the most important thing to pay attention is gender while scoring."

S₂: "The questions should not be directed towards learning only little information. Much knowledge should be obtained by one question."

S₇: "It should be checked whether the appropriate style, appeal and selected words are appropriate for their age."

S₆: "It is necessary for the teacher to be in a position to manage the process and the result, and to guide this process."

S₂₃: "It should be paid attention to be fair and age group should be considered. Assessment should be carried out with empathy."

Table 3: Views on Positive Aspects of Peer Assessment

Codes	Student/s	f
Identifying inadequate aspects	S ₁₀ , S ₁₃ , S ₁₄ , S ₁₆ , S ₁₈ , S ₂₅ , S ₂₇ , S ₂₈ , S ₂₉ , S ₃₀ , S ₃₄ , S ₃₈ , S ₄₀ , S ₄₃	14
Empathize	S ₅ , S ₉ , S ₃₁ , S ₃₂ , S ₃₃ , S ₃₆ , S ₃₇ , S ₄₇	8
Democracy	S ₅ , S ₆ , S ₈ , S ₁₁ , S ₂₀	5
Finding the right	S ₂ , S ₇ , S ₁₅ , S ₃₀	4
Enhancing Self-Confidence	S ₃ , S ₁₆ , S ₃₄ , S ₄₂	4
Similar and different aspects	S ₁₂ , S ₁₉ , S ₃₁ , S ₃₅	4
Feedback	S ₁₆ , S ₂₃ , S ₂₆ , S ₃₉	4
Ability of Self-expression	S ₁ , S ₂₇ , S ₄₄	3
Socialization	S ₁ , S ₆ , S ₂₂	3
Peer recognition	S ₂₄ , S ₄₁ , S ₄₆	3
Motivation	S ₄ , S ₈	2
Ability to assess	S ₆ , S ₄₄	2
Critical thinking	S ₁₄	1
Placement	S ₁₇	1
Approximate Success Level	S ₂₁	1
Ability to analyze	S ₃₄	1
Enhancing Level of Knowledge and Experience	S ₄₇	1
It is not positive	S ₄₅	1

Table 3 shows the views of prospective Turkish language teachers on the positive aspects of peer assessment. When Table 3 is examined, it is seen that prospective Turkish language teachers handled the positive aspects of peer assessment under 18 title such as: identifying inadequate aspects, empathize, democracy, finding the right, enhancing self-confidence, similar and different aspects, feedback, ability of self-expression, socialization, peer recognition, motivation, ability to assess, critical thinking, ability to analyze, enhancing level of knowledge and experience, and it is not positive. Among these, the identifying inadequacies has been mostly mentioned under f: 14 title while determining critical thinking, approximate success level, placement, ability to analyze have been least mentioned under f: 6 title. It is possible to present some of the views expressed by the students as follows:

S₁₀: "To enable the person to see the defects."

S₃₄: "It is important for the students to see the mistakes in order to notice the inadequacies."

S₄₇: "The evaluator is able to empathize easily with the individual who is evaluated by herself/himself than a teacher does while making evaluation."

S₅: "We have improved the understanding of democracy by means of this evaluation."

S₂: "By revealing inadequate and excessive aspects of individuals, individual is canalized to the correct one."

S₄₂: "Positive assessments help to increase the self-confidence of the child. It contributes to the child's individual development."

S₃₅: "It helps individuals to be aware of each other and to learn their advantages and weaknesses compared to others."

S₃₉: "The views of the peers are very significant in determining the level that the students reached."

S₂₇: *“The individual understands inadequate aspects or the area that s/he comprehensively know. The substantiality of expression strengthens.”*

S₂₂: *“We may have the opportunity to learn the attitude of the students in the class towards each other and the results of the behavior that they expect from each other.”*

S₄₆: *“Ensuring that people in the class or in the same age group see themselves.”*

S₄: *“Since it expresses the positive aspect of the individual, it is motivating, and it provides awareness.”*

S₄₄: *“One of the positive aspects of peer assessment is enhancing the ability of students to make assessment.”*

S₁₄: *“It develops critical thinking.”*

Table 4: Views on Negative Aspects of Peer Assessment

Codes	Student/s	f
Acting with feelings	S ₃ , S ₅ , S ₆ , S ₇ , S ₈ , S ₉ , S ₁₁ , S ₁₂ , S ₁₃ , S ₁₆ , S ₂₀ , S ₂₁ , S ₂₃ , S ₂₄ , S ₂₆ , S ₃₁ , S ₃₂ , S ₃₃ , S ₃₄ , S ₃₅ , S ₃₆ , S ₃₇ , S ₃₈ , S ₃₉ , S ₄₀ , S ₄₁ , S ₄₂ , S ₄₄ , S ₄₅ , S ₄₆	30
Lack of Self-Confidence	S ₁ , S ₁₀ , S ₁₄ , S ₁₅ , S ₁₇ , S ₁₈ , S ₂₈ , S ₂₉ , S ₃₀ , S ₃₁ , S ₄₃	11
Competence for Assessment	S ₁₆ , S ₁₉ , S ₄₇	3
Excitement	S ₄ , S ₂₇	2
Just making assessment not efficient	S ₂₂ , S ₄₇	2
Restricting expression of opinion	S ₂	1
Disregarding opinions of the peers	S ₂₅	1

Table 4 has shown the views of the prospective Turkish teachers regarding the negative aspects of peer assessment. When Table 4 is examined, it is seen that Turkish teacher candidates handled the negative aspects of peer assessment under 7 titles. These are acting with feelings, lack of self-confidence, competence for assessment, excitement, just making assessment not efficient, restricting expression of opinions, and disregarding opinions of the peers. Among them acting with feelings has been mostly expressed under f: 30 titles while restricting expression of opinions and disregarding opinions of the peers have been least mentioned under f: 2 title. Some of them have been listed below:

S₈: *“Students may keep negative opinions about their friends that they do not like in their minds and these negative opinions may affect the teacher’s mind.”*

S₁₅: *“If individual does not objectively think/act, the other individual may be offended and discouraged.”*

S₁₉: *“Sometimes when we assess individuals who are at the same age, we consider them as if they have the same characteristic features. If we do not see the differences between them and equate them all as if they are same, it will not give positive results.”*

S₂₅: *“Negative aspects cannot be detected because they are at the same age as the evaluator.”*

Table 5: Views on Peer Assessment by the Peers

Codes	Student/s	f
Awareness raising	S ₁ , S ₂ , S ₄ , S ₅ , S ₆ , S ₇ , S ₉ , S ₁₁ , S ₁₆ , S ₁₈ , S ₂₁ , S ₂₂ , S ₂₃ , S ₂₄ , S ₂₆ , S ₂₉ , S ₃₄ , S ₃₇ , S ₄₁ , S ₄₂	20
Objective	S ₈ , S ₁₂ , S ₁₃ , S ₁₄ , S ₂₈ , S ₃₀ , S ₃₂ , S ₃₃ , S ₃₈ , S ₃₉ , S ₄₀ , S ₄₆	12
Openness to assessment	S ₆ , S ₁₀ , S ₁₆ , S ₁₇ , S ₄₅	5
Approximate success level	S ₃ , S ₁₉ , S ₂₀	3
Strong communication among the peers	S ₈ , S ₉ , S ₄₇	3
Tolerance	S ₅ , S ₃₅	2
Enhancing ability to assess	S ₂₅ , S ₂₇	2
Choosing appropriate topic	S ₁₅	1
It should not be often carried out	S ₃₁	1
Empathy	S ₃₆	1
Increasing attention	S ₄₃	1
Different point of view	S ₄₄	1

Table 5 has shown the views of prospective Turkish teachers on peer assessment. When Table 5 is examined, it is seen that the views of prospective Turkish teachers have been assessed by their peers under 12 titles. These are awareness raising, objectivity, openness to assessment, approximate level of success, strong communication among the peers, tolerance, enhancing ability to assess, choosing appropriate topic, it should not be often carried out, empathy, increasing attention and different point of view. Among these, awareness raising mostly stated under f: 20 title while choosing appropriate topic, it should not be often carried out, empathy, increasing attention and different point of view have been least stated under f: 5 title. It is possible to introduce some of the views expressed by the students as follows:

S₁: *“In the past, I did not care for anyone who evaluates what I did because I was not open to criticism. But I have tried to consider the assessments about me that made by my peers as I have become a conscious individual thanks to conscious assessments.”*

S₂₅: *“An objective assessment allows us to see our inadequate aspects. An unnecessary assessment may cause being abashed.”*

S₆: *“I would like to be criticized and assessed by other prospective teachers as a prospective teacher.”*

S₁₉: *“While making assessment, the most distinctive aspects should be identified at first and then peers at the same level should be assessed.”*

S₈: *“In my opinion, it is very good indeed. However, if objective and reasonable assessments are made, it can be very useful. Because, our peers can talk to us in a more comfortable manner and they approach us closer.”*

S₅: *“Criticism is important in terms of being open to criticism, being able to see our inadequacies, being fair and tolerant, and contributing to our ability to score and assess in teaching.”*

S₂₇: *“The assessment contributes to the maturation of the individual in her/his branch and to develop ability of assessment of the evaluator.”*

S₄₄: "I think peer assessment should be carried out. Because this assessment can give us different perspectives and can help us to improve ourselves."

Table 6: Views on Recommendations for Peer Assessment

Codes	Student/s	f
Impartiality	S ₁ , S ₄ , S ₅ , S ₆ , S ₈ , S ₉ , S ₁₄ , S ₁₅ , S ₁₆ , S ₁₇ , S ₂₁ , S ₂₃ , S ₂₄ , S ₂₆ , S ₂₉ , S ₃₁ , S ₃₂ , S ₃₄ , S ₃₅ , S ₃₆ , S ₃₈ , S ₃₉ , S ₄₁ , S ₄₅	24
Knowledge for making criticism	S ₆ , S ₇ , S ₁₅ , S ₁₈ , S ₂₅ , S ₂₆ , S ₂₇ , S ₂₈ , S ₃₇ , S ₄₂ , S ₄₃ , S ₄₄ , S ₄₆	13
Individual differences Consideration	S ₂ , S ₁₀ , S ₁₁ , S ₁₉ , S ₂₀ , S ₂₂ , S ₃₃	7
Appropriate environment for assessment	S ₉ , S ₁₃ , S ₃₀	3
It should be more often carried out	S ₁₂ , S ₄₇	2
Consistency	S ₈	1
Communication among the students	S ₃	1
It should not be carried out	S ₄₀	1
Approximate success level	S ₁₆	1

Table 6 has shown the views on recommendations for peer assessment of prospective Turkish teachers. When Table 6 is examined, it is seen that the views of prospective Turkish language teachers on peer assessment have been handled under 9 titles such as impartiality, knowledge for making criticism, individual differences, consideration, appropriate environment for assessment, it should be more often carried out, consistency, communication among students, it should not be carried out, approximate success level. Among these, impartiality has been mostly expressed under f: 24 title; while consistency, communication among the students, approximate success level and it should not be carried out have been least stated under f: 4 title. Some of the views expressed by the students as follows:

S₉: "Different practices can be developed to be impartial for making judgments and objectivity. Environments that allow peers to assess more easily can be provided."

S₇: "The level of criticism should be moderate."

S₂₀: "Every individual is different in terms of his/her unique characteristics. That is why an equal assessment should be made."

S₃₀: "I find it more appropriate to make peer assessment by criteria of framework that determined in written form."

S₁₂: "Peer assessment should be carried out."

S₈: "Consistent assessment will be more reliable. A reliable result can be achieved if the assessments are objective, consistent and reasonably framed."

S₃: *“Students who have approximate success level should be involved in this process. Another problem is that some students may not like each other. This negatively affects the assessment.”*

S₁₆: *“While peer assessment is carrying out, the scoring must be objective and there should be no difference between the evaluator and the individual who is evaluated in terms of level of knowledge and skills.”*

4. Conclusion

In this study which aims to determine the views of prospective Turkish language teachers on peer assessment, it has been determined that prospective Turkish language teachers have defined the peer assessment under the categories such as the assessment of the individuals who are at the same age, peer comparison, alternative measurement tool and realizing positive and negative aspects. The definitions of peer assessment have been shaped around the peer assessment title.

The views of the prospective Turkish language teachers on the points to be considered when scoring in peer assessment have been analyzed under the categories of justice, scientificness, forming scoring rubric, individual difference, expediency, gender, scrutinizing questions, moral values, and observation and teacher guidance. It has been argued that the most significant feature in this part is to provide a fair environment for assessment.

Positive views of prospective Turkish language teachers on peer assessment have been categorized such as identifying inadequate aspects, empathize, democracy, finding the right, enhancing self-confidence, similar and different aspects, feedback, ability of self-expression, socialization, peer recognition, motivation, ability to assess, critical thinking, ability to analyze, enhancing level of knowledge and experience, and it is not positive. The most positive aspect of peer assessment is the view that points out realizing inadequacies.

Negative opinions about peer assessment of prospective Turkish language teachers have been determined as acting with feelings, lack of self-confidence, competence for assessment, excitement, just making assessment not efficient, restricting expression of opinions, and disregarding opinions of the peers. It has been seen that acting with feeling has been determined as the most negative aspect of the peer assessment.

It has been found out that the views of prospective Turkish language teachers on peer assessment are generally positive. The views on prospective Turkish language teachers on peer assessment that carried out by their peers have been determined under categories such as awareness raising, objectivity, openness to assessment, approximate level of success, strong communication among the peers, tolerance, enhancing ability to assess, choosing appropriate topic, it should not be often carried out, empathy, increasing attention and different point of view

The recommendations of prospective Turkish language teachers on peer assessment have been determined under the categories such as impartiality,

knowledge for making criticism, individual differences, consideration, appropriate environment for assessment, it should be more often carried out, consistency, communication among students, it should not be carried out, approximate success level.

When the interview form is examined, it is seen that all of the prospective Turkish language teachers are interested in subjects such as impartiality, scientificness, objectivity, justice, having knowledge of criticism, applying scoring scale and not acting with feelings.

4.1 Recommendations

- Prospective Turkish language teachers should be informed about how to make criticism.
- Activities related to peer assessment should be carried out in Special Teaching Methods I, Special Teaching Methods II, Measurement and Evaluation courses.
- The application process of those taught in the Teaching Practice course should be followed carefully.

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